

INFLUENCE OF THE DURATION OF RENAL REPLACEMENT THERAPY ON THE CONDITION OF THE GASTRODUODENAL ZONE

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ABSTRACT

Patients with stage V chronic kidney disease (CKD) undergoing maintenance hemodialysis frequently develop lesions of the gastroduodenal zone. Uremic intoxication, microcirculatory disturbances, chronic inflammation, mucosal hypoxia, and long-term pharmacological therapy contribute to the development of gastropathies, erosive, and ulcerative lesions. The influence of hemodialysis duration on the severity of gastroduodenal disorders remains an important clinical issue requiring further investigation.

Significance: Patients with stage V chronic kidney disease (CKD) undergoing maintenance hemodialysis frequently develop lesions of the gastroduodenal zone. Uremic intoxication, microcirculatory disturbances, chronic inflammation, mucosal hypoxia, and long-term pharmacological therapy contribute to the development of gastropathies, erosive, and ulcerative lesions. The influence of hemodialysis duration on the severity of gastroduodenal disorders remains an important clinical issue requiring further investigation.

Objective: To assess the influence of the duration of maintenance hemodialysis on the condition of the gastroduodenal zone in patients with stage V CKD.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical Medical Center of Nephrology and Kidney Transplantation during 2024–2025. A total of 60 patients with stage V CKD receiving maintenance hemodialysis were enrolled in the study. Depending on the duration of hemodialysis, the patients were divided into three groups: Group I — hemodialysis duration less than 1 year (n=20); Group II — 1–5 years (n=20); Group III — more than 5 years (n=20). The mean age of the patients was 48.6 ± 11.4 years. The study population included 36 men (60.0%) and 24 women (40.0%). All patients underwent bicarbonate hemodialysis three times weekly according to the standard treatment protocol. The examination included clinical and anamnestic assessment, laboratory investigations, and esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD). Endoscopic evaluation assessed the presence of chronic gastritis, duodenitis, as well as erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results: An increase in the frequency and severity of gastroduodenal lesions was observed with longer duration of maintenance hemodialysis. Chronic gastritis was detected in 50.0% of patients in Group I, 70.0% in Group II, and 90.0% in Group III ($\chi^2=7.62$; $p=0.022$). The prevalence of duodenitis was 30.0%, 50.0%, and 75.0%, respectively ($\chi^2=8.14$; $p=0.017$). Erosive lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa were diagnosed in 20.0% of patients receiving hemodialysis for less than 1 year, 40.0% of patients undergoing dialysis for 1–5 years, and 70.0% of patients treated for more than 5 years ($\chi^2=10.32$; $p=0.006$). Dyspeptic symptoms, including nausea, epigastric heaviness, and decreased appetite, were also more common in patients with longer dialysis duration: 35.0%, 60.0%, and 80.0%, respectively ($\chi^2=8.37$; $p=0.015$). Ulcerative lesions were observed less frequently and did not demonstrate statistically significant differences between the groups ($\chi^2=3.75$; $p=0.153$).

Conclusions: The duration of maintenance hemodialysis significantly affects the condition of the gastroduodenal zone. Patients undergoing hemodialysis for more than 5 years demonstrated a significantly higher prevalence of chronic gastritis, duodenitis, and erosive lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa. These findings indicate the need for regular gastroenterological and endoscopic monitoring in this category of patients for early detection and timely correction of gastroduodenal pathology.

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